

DYNAMICAL MODELLING OF THE CHAIN STRUCTURE FORMATION IN ELECTRORHEOLOGICAL FLUIDS

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SUMMARY: An electrorheological fluid consists of a suspension of fine particles in a liquid of low dielectric constant and low viscosity. Its apparent viscosity increases dramatically in the presence of an electric field. Experimental investigations reveal that as the electric field is applied, the depolarized particles form a chain structure along the electric field, and the formation of chains underlies all phenomena of ER fluid. In this paper, the released electromagnetic energy accompanying the growth of the chain was derived first based on a dynamic electromagnetic solution. The released energy, serving as the driving force for the chain formation, should equal to the dissipated energy related with friction resistance of the viscous fluid in the chain formation. In such way, the governing differential equation of the chain growth was established. Based on this energy model, the velocity of the chain forming, and the response time of ER fluid can be predicted.

KEYWORDS: ER fluid, Chain formation, Mechanism, Energy approach, Dynamic model

INTRODUCTION

An electrorheological (ER) fluid consists of a suspension of fine particles in a liquid of low dielectric constant and low viscosity. Its apparent viscosity increases dramatically in the presence of an applied electric field. If the electric field exceeds a critical value, the ER fluid turns into a solid whose yield stress increases as the field is further strengthened. This phenomenon is completely reversible. Upon electric field cutoff, the system immediately resumes its original liquid state. The time scale for the transition is of the order of millisecond. The phenomenon of electrorheology was first discovered by Winslow (1949), and is sometimes termed the “Winslow effect”. Because of their fast response and low power requirements, ER fluids provide the possibility of rapid-response coupling between mechanical devices and electronic control. These properties also make ER fluid attractive for many futuristic technologies. To predict the response and design optimally the high performance ER fluid, a crucial problem is to gain a clear understanding of the physical mechanism of the ER phenomenon. Let us consider a system of small particles of dielectric constant ϵ_p suspended in a fluid of dielectric constant ϵ_f , $\epsilon_p > \epsilon_f$. The whole system is placed between two parallel plates, upon which a voltage is applied to produce an electric

field. When the dielectric particles have a density close to the liquid density, the buoyant force neutralizes the gravity and creates a low-gravity environment. Before applying the electric field, the thermal motion makes particles randomly distributed in the space and forms a uniform liquid suspension. As the electric field is applied, the particles obtain an induced dipole moment. When the applied electric field increases, the depolarized particles will begin to aggregate one another, and form a chain structure along the electric field. Due to the formation of these chains, the shear strength and viscosity of ER fluid increase by orders. Therefore, the formation of chains underlies all phenomena of ER fluid.

Many researches have been carried out to understand the mechanism of the structure formation. Tao *et al* [1989, 1991a, b, 1992] published a series of works about the structure formation in ER fluid under the action of the external field based on phase transition theory from a disordered state to an ordered state. Klingenberg *et al.*[1989, 1990, 1993] carried out two- and three-dimensional molecular-dynamics-like simulation on the structure formation in electrorheological suspensions. Conrad *et al.* [1991, 1994, 1995] carried out a series theoretical and experimental investigations on the response of ER fluids. And these investigations also motivated many fruitful research works later on. Recently much effort is being devoted to the synthesis of new ER fluids possessing desirable rheological, electrical, chemical, and tribological properties. Receiving particular attention are those materials that exhibit large yield stress and short response time of the field-induced structure change. Detailed descriptions of the research on the mechanism can be found in the excellent review paper by Parthasarathy and Klingenberg (1996)

To use ER fluid successfully in engineering and develop some high performance material, it is important to understand the mechanism by which the ER structure is formed, and to reveal the nature of the structural kinetics, and the role of the structure in determining the mechanical properties of the ER materials. In this paper, we treat the aggregating process of polarized particles as a dynamic process. By assuming the forming column as a prolate spheroid, the induced electric and magnetic field around the chain were obtained, then the released electromagnetic energy accompanying the growth of the chain was derived. The released energy, serving as the driving force for the chain formation, should equal to the dissipated energy related with friction resistance of the viscous fluid in the chain formation. In such way, the governing differential equation of the chain growth was established. Based on this energy model, the velocity of the chain forming, and the response time of ER fluid can be predicted. The present model can also predict the effect of temperature and some microstructural parameters, such as the dielectric constants and concentration of the particles, etc., on the response of an ER system.

2.GENERAL SOLUTIONS OF ELECTRIC AND MAGNETIC FIELDS AROUND THE AGGREGATE OF THE POLARIZED PARTICLES

Consider that a suspension of fine dielectric particles in a liquid of low dielectric constants is put between two parallel plates, when the applied electric field is zero or very small, the thermal motion makes the particles randomly distributed in the space and form a uniform suspension (Fig. 1). As the electric field increases, the particles obtain an induced dipolar moment, which can be expressed in the form as

$$\bar{p} = \alpha a^3 \epsilon_f \bar{E} \quad (1)$$

where a is the particle radius, $\alpha = (\epsilon_p - \epsilon_f)/(\epsilon_p + 2\epsilon_f)$ and \bar{E} is the local effective field acting on the particles and \bar{E} can be approximated by the applied electric field. The polarization or the electric dipole moment density \bar{P}_s is given as follows,

$$\bar{P}_s = \bar{p}/v_a = \frac{3}{4\pi} \alpha \epsilon_f \bar{E} \quad (2)$$

where v_a is the volume of a single particle.

The polarized particles intend to aggregate one another along the direction of the applied field to reduce the free energy of the system, and form the chains (Fig.1). In what follows, we only consider the formation of one representative chain. The aggregation of the polarized particle is assumed to take the shape of prolate spheroid with the aspect ratio $\beta = a_3/a_1$, and $a_3 > a_1 = a_2$ is the principle half axes. This assumption will induce some error in the analysis. But we do not think it is a very strict restriction. Since the chain will grow dynamically, it will induce an electric field and magnetic field around the chain, which can be derived according to Wang and Xiao (1998) as follows.

Now the problem becomes that in an infinite dielectric medium with dielectric constant ϵ_f there is a growing prolate spheroid inclusion with the same dielectric constant but with a polarization \vec{P}_s under the action of an applied electric field \vec{E} . The induced polarization \vec{P}_s is due to that the particles have a much larger dielectric constant than the fluid. Under such an assumption, our analysis will be simplified a great deal. After solving the Maxwell equation, the electric field can be obtained in the form as:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= -\frac{p_s x_1}{4\pi\epsilon_f} \frac{\partial I_1(\lambda)}{\partial x_3}, \\ E_2 &= -\frac{p_s x_2}{4\pi\epsilon_f} \frac{\partial I_1(\lambda)}{\partial x_3}, \\ E_3 &= E_3^e - \frac{P_s}{4\pi\epsilon_f} [I_3(\lambda) + x_3 \frac{\partial I_3(\lambda)}{\partial x_3} + \frac{1}{c_f^2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\lambda)}{\partial t^2}], \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\Phi(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2}[I(\lambda) - x_n x_n I_N(\lambda)]$, $x_n x_n I_N(\lambda) = x_1^2 I_1(\lambda) + x_2^2 I_2(\lambda) + x_3^2 I_3(\lambda)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} I(\lambda) &= \frac{4\pi a_1 a_3}{\sqrt{\beta^2 - 1}} \arccos h\bar{b} \\ I_3(\lambda) &= 4\pi\beta(\arccos h\bar{b} - \bar{d}/\bar{b})/(\beta^2 - 1)^{3/2} \\ I_1(\lambda) = I_2(\lambda) &= 2\pi\beta(\bar{b}\bar{d} - \arccos h\bar{b})/(\beta^2 - 1)^{3/2} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{b} = \sqrt{(a_3^2 + \lambda)/(a_1^2 + \lambda)}$, $\bar{d} = \sqrt{(a_3^2 - a_1^2)/(a_1^2 + \lambda)}$, and λ is the largest positive root of the equation

$$\frac{x_1^2}{(a_1^2 + \lambda)} + \frac{x_2^2}{(a_2^2 + \lambda)} + \frac{x_3^2}{(a_3^2 + \lambda)} = 1. \quad (5)$$

When \bar{x} is inside the inclusion, $\lambda = 0$. According to Mura (1987, eqn.11.40.4), one can write

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{,ij} &= -\delta_{ij} I_I(\lambda) - x_i I_{I,j}(\lambda) \\ \Phi_{,m} &= -x_m I_M(\lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

in which we have superposed the applied electric field E_3^e . For the internal points, $\lambda = 0$, therefore, $E_1^l = E_2^l = 0$. The magnetic field can also be derived as follows:

$$\vec{H} = \frac{P_s}{4\pi} (x_1 \vec{j} - x_2 \vec{i}) \frac{\partial I_1(\lambda)}{\partial t}, \quad (7)$$

where $I_1(\lambda)$ keeps continuous when $\lambda \rightarrow 0$, therefore, on the surface of the chain $\vec{H}^l = \vec{H}^o$.

Figure 1. Schema of the chain formation process of the particles in ER fluid under the action of an applied electric field

3. EXPLICIT EXPRESSION OF THE DRIVING FORCE FOR THE CHAIN GROWTH

3.1 General formulation of electromagnetic driving force

If we consider the ER fluid as a global system in which the interaction conditions are: the external electric field, temperature and pressure keep constant as

$$\vec{E}^e = const, \quad T = const, \quad p = 0, \quad (8)$$

in the equilibrium state, one can write out the condition (Stchev, 1973).

$$\begin{aligned}
d\Gamma &= dW - dU + TdS \\
&= dL,
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where W is the input energy by outside environment, U is the internal electromagnetic energy of the system, S is the entropy of the system, and L is the energy dissipation of the system. Equation (9) means that the input energy will be used to balance the energy dissipation for the process besides compensating the internal energy increase and the entropy decrease of the system. Therefore similar to the energy-momentum tensor defined by Eshelby (1970), $\frac{d\Gamma}{d\beta}$

serves as the driving force for the chain to grow. With the formation of the chain structures, the system is getting more and more ordered, as a result, the entropy of the system decreases, i. e., $dS < 0$. From equation (9) one can easily find out with the temperature increasing, more energy is needed for the formation of the chain. In other words, one needs to apply a stronger electric field to realize the transition. In what follows, we will express the terms in equation (9) one by one explicitly.

3.2. The electromagnetic energy of spherical particles

First by assuming that the particle in ER fluid is taken the spherical shape, the expression of electromagnetic energy can be derived. Consider a spherical polarized particle with polarization \bar{p}_s in a homogenous dielectric material under the action of the external electric field, the internal electromagnetic energy can be obtained as:

$$f = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V \bar{E} \cdot \bar{D} dv = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V (\bar{E}^e + \Delta\bar{E}) \cdot (\bar{D}^e + \Delta\bar{D}) dv \tag{10}$$

where \bar{E}^e , \bar{D}^e are the applied electric field and the corresponding electric displacement, $\Delta\bar{E}$, $\Delta\bar{D}$ are the induced electric field and displacement due to the polarization prescribed in the particle \bar{p}_s , which can be treated as the free charges in the following derivation. The electrostatic energy, therefore, becomes

$$f = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V E_i^e D_i^e dv - \iiint_{\Omega} E_i^e p_i^s dv - \frac{1}{2} \iiint_{\Omega} \Delta E_i p_i^s dv, \tag{11}$$

where Ω is the region occupied by the particle. The first term in equation (11) is the electromagnetic energy caused by the applied electric field without the particle, therefore, the interaction energy caused by introducing a single particle is

$$\Delta f = - \iiint_{\Omega} E_i^e p_i^s dv - \frac{1}{2} \iiint_{\Omega} \Delta E_i p_i^s dv, \tag{12}$$

For constant polarization and spherical inclusion, $\Delta\bar{E}$ is given by $\Delta\bar{E} = -\frac{P_s}{6\epsilon} \bar{k}$. Consider that

there are N polarized particles in the element of ER fluid, the polarization can be expressed in the form as $P_s = \sum_{i=1}^N p_s H(\Omega_i)$. The total interaction energy is obtained from

$$\Delta F = - \iiint_{\Omega} E_i^e P_i^s dv - \frac{1}{2} \iiint_{\Omega} \Delta E_i (P_s) P_i^s dv, \tag{13}$$

If we assume that the chain is formed by attracting particles to aggregate one by one along the direction of the applied field, the number of the separated particles in the element will decrease with time. Therefore, the change rate of the electromagnetic energy with the reduction of separated particles is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\dot{U} &= \frac{d(\Delta F)}{dt} \\ &= [-\iiint_{\Omega} E_i^e p_i^s dv - \iiint_{\Omega} \Delta E_i p_i^s dv] \frac{dN}{dt},\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

in which $\Delta E_i(P_s)$ is the linear function of P_s . In the following analysis, we consider the perturbation of the electric field inside a particle depends only on the polarization inside that particle, and neglect the influence of the other particles.

3.3 The electromagnetic energy of the spheroidal chain

From another point of view, part of the electromagnetic energy will disappear with the reduction of separated particles. At the same time, part of the electromagnetic energy will appear with the aggregation of particles. Next we consider the change rate of the electromagnetic energy accompanying the growth of the chain. In the finite element V of the ER fluid there is a chain of polarized particles (Fig.1). The internal energy of the chain under the action of the applied field is given by [Frankl, 1986]

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V (\bar{E} \cdot \bar{D} + \bar{H} \cdot \bar{B}) dv, \quad (15)$$

where V is the total volume of the ER material element. The change rate of the internal energy is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{U} &= \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{1}{2} \iiint_V (\bar{E} \cdot \bar{D} + \bar{H} \cdot \bar{B}) dv \right] \\ &= \iiint_V (\bar{E} \cdot \dot{\bar{D}} + \bar{H} \cdot \dot{\bar{B}}) dv \\ &= \iiint_V [-\bar{E} \cdot \bar{J} - \nabla \cdot (\bar{E} \times \bar{H})] dv.\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

In deriving equation (16), we have used the Maxwell equation (3) to replace the time-derivative factors in the integrand. Equation (16) is known as *Poynting's theorem*. $\bar{S} = \bar{E} \times \bar{H}$, where \bar{S} is called the *Poynting vector*, which is identified as the energy flux, or energy flow rate per unit area.

the electric current density can be derived as follows:

$$\bar{J} = \frac{\partial \bar{P}}{\partial t} = p_s \bar{k} \frac{\partial H[\Omega(t)]}{\partial t}. \quad (17)$$

If the surface of the chain is expressed in the form of $r=R(t)$, as a result, the first term in equation (16) is expressed as

$$-\iiint_V \bar{J} \cdot \bar{E} dv = -p_s \iint_S E_3^l \dot{R}(t) ds \quad (18)$$

where S is the surface of the chain. For the second term of equation (16), we can not use Gauss theorem directly since across the surface of the chain, the integrand is not continuous. So we divide the integral into two parts:

$$\begin{aligned}\iiint_V \nabla \cdot \bar{S} dv &= \iiint_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot \bar{S} dv + \iiint_{V-\Omega} \nabla \cdot \bar{S} dv \\ &= \iint_{\Gamma} \bar{S} \cdot d\bar{s} - \iint_S [\bar{S}] \cdot d\bar{s}\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

where S^+, S^- are the internal and external surfaces of the chain, Γ is the surface of the whole ER system, $d\bar{s}$ is the surface element along the outward normal direction of the chain, and

$$[\bar{S}] = \bar{S}^- - \bar{S}^+. \quad (20)$$

3.4. The input energy by outside environment

The rate of the energy input by the outside environment through the boundary Γ is given by

$$\dot{W} = -\iint_{\Gamma} \bar{S} \cdot d\bar{s}. \quad (21)$$

3.5. The expression of the energy release rate

Substitution of equations (14), (16) and (21) into equation (9) gives the released energy rate:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{G} &= \dot{W} - \dot{U} + \Delta\dot{U} + T\dot{S} \\ &= \iint_s \{p_s E_3^I \dot{R}(t) - [S_i] n_i\} ds + \Delta\dot{U} + T\dot{S}, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where the integration is carried out on the surface of the chain. The energy release rate \dot{G} represents the driving force for the growth of the chain. With the aid of the expressions of the electric and magnetic field both inside and outside the inclusion, the change rate of the energy is given by

$$\dot{G} = \frac{p_s^2}{\epsilon_f} \frac{dN}{dt} v_a \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{I_3(\beta)}{8\pi} \right] - \frac{p_s^2}{4\pi\epsilon_f c_f^2} \iint_{\Gamma} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial t^2} \dot{R}(t) ds + T\dot{S}, \quad (23)$$

The energy release rate can also be expressed in the form of

$$\dot{G} = g \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial t}, \quad (29)$$

where $g = \frac{\partial G}{\partial \beta}$ is the energy reduction per unit increase of the aspect ratio of the chain, and

$$\frac{\partial \beta}{\partial t} = \frac{dN}{dt}, \quad (30)$$

where $\frac{dN}{dt}$ is the increasing rate of the particles aggregating on the chain. From equation (29), one can find

$$g = \frac{p_s^2}{\epsilon_f} v_a \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{I_3(\beta)}{8\pi} \right] - \frac{p_s^2}{4\pi\epsilon_f c_f^2} \iint_{\Gamma} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial t^2} \frac{\partial R}{\partial \beta} ds + T \frac{\partial S}{\partial \beta}, \quad (31)$$

where $\frac{\partial S}{\partial \beta}$ is the change rate of the entropy versus the aspect ratio. Equation (31) can be rewritten in the form as

$$g = A(\beta) \frac{d^2 \beta}{dt^2} + B(\beta) \left(\frac{d\beta}{dt} \right)^2 + C(\beta), \quad (32)$$

where

$$A(\beta) = \frac{p_s^2}{8\pi\epsilon_f c_f^2} \iint_{\Gamma} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \beta} \frac{\partial R}{\partial \beta} ds, \quad (33)$$

$$B(\beta) = -\frac{p_s^2}{8\pi\epsilon_f c_f^2} \iint_{\Gamma} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \beta^2} \frac{\partial R}{\partial \beta} ds, \quad (34)$$

$$C(\beta) = \frac{p_s^2}{\epsilon_f} v_a \left[\frac{1}{6} - \frac{I_3(\beta)}{8\pi} \right] + T \frac{\partial S}{\partial \beta}. \quad (35)$$

4. SOME RESULTS PREDICTED BY THE MODEL

From equation (32), it is very clear that the energy release rate, or the driving force of the chain growth, is a function of the speed of the chain growth. This is similar to the case of

dynamic fracture mechanics (Freund, 1990), where the energy release rate is a function of the velocity of crack growth. From the view of energy conservation, the released energy should be used to overcome the friction force created by the fluid on the particles when they are moving to aggregate into a chain. If the velocity of the particles is denoted as η , the friction force created by the fluid on the particle is

$$f = \bar{\mu} \eta \quad (36)$$

where $\bar{\mu}$ is the generalized viscosity. One can also assume that the particle needs to move a distance Δx , which depends on the concentration of particles, to join the chain. The work done by the system for a particle joining the chain is given by

$$\Delta W = f \Delta x = \bar{\mu} \eta \Delta x. \quad (37)$$

The time needed for a particle to join the chain is

$$\Delta t = \frac{\Delta x}{\eta} \quad (38)$$

During this time, the aspect ratio β will increase by one, therefore

$$\eta = \frac{d\beta}{dt} \Delta x \quad (39)$$

Substitution of equation (39) into equation (37) yields

$$\Delta W = f \Delta x = \bar{\mu} \Delta x^2 \frac{d\beta}{dt}. \quad (40)$$

Equation (40) means that the resistance energy for the chain formation is in proportion to the velocity of the aspect ratio change. The energy conservation equation is given by

$$\begin{aligned} g &= A(\beta) \frac{d^2\beta}{dt^2} + B(\beta) \left(\frac{d\beta}{dt} \right)^2 + C(\beta) \\ &= \Delta W = \bar{\mu} \Delta x^2 \frac{d\beta}{dt} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Equation (41) is the governing equation of the chain growth based on our energy model.

The parameter c_f in the expression of $B(\beta)$ represents the propagation speed of electromagnetic wave in the fluid. It should be much larger than the speed of the chain growth $d\beta/dt$, therefore the second term in equation (41) can be neglected. For stationary growth of the chain, $\frac{d^2\beta}{dt^2} = 0$. Equation (41) becomes:

$$C(\beta) = \bar{\mu} \Delta x^2 \frac{d\beta}{dt} \quad (42)$$

The average moving distance for a particle to join the chain can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta x = k \left(\frac{v_f}{v_a} \right)^{-1/3} \quad (43)$$

where v_f is the volume fraction of the particles, v_a is the volume of a single particle, and k is a constant. If one takes Δx equal to the average distance between the particles, $k \approx 0.57$ (Wang and Duan, 1992).

The velocity of the aspect ratio change versus the aspect ratio $\beta (=a_3/a_1)$ is shown in Fig.2, where $I_3(\beta)$ is given by equation (20) by assigning $\lambda = 0$. When the aspect ratio approaches infinity, $C(\beta)$ approaches its maximum value. For an adiabatic system, the last term in equation (32) becomes zero. As a result, the maximum value of the chain growth speed is given by

$$\left(\frac{d\beta}{dt}\right)_{\max} = \frac{p_s^2 v_a}{6\epsilon_f \bar{\mu} \Delta x^2}. \quad (44)$$

The time needed for the chain to cross the distance between the electrodes is also given by equation (42), which is shown in Fig.3, where $t^* = \bar{\mu} \epsilon_f \Delta x^2 / (p_s^2 v_a)$. From figures 3 and 4, one can find that the chain grows in a uniform speed soon after it starts to propagate.

If we define the critical field for the phase transition as the minimum value of the applied electric field to induce the chain formation, this electric field can be determined by assigning the energy release rate equal to zero:

$$C(\beta) = 0 \quad (45)$$

When $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, one can determine the lower bound of the electric field that induces the transition happening:

$$E_c = \sqrt{\frac{32\pi^2 RT}{3\alpha^2 \epsilon_f v_a}} \quad (46)$$

where $R = -\frac{\partial S}{\partial \beta}$. Based on this model, one need first to know the entropy change accompanying the chain formation process to incorporate the effect of temperature. We do not know how to determine it at this stage, and in our analysis, we did not take the boundary effect of the electrodes into consideration. The effect of the dielectric properties of the particles is reflected through the parameter p_s . At last, it should be mentioned that some novel phenomena predicted by the present model need to be verified by experimental data.

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Figure 2. The velocity of the chain growth $t^* \frac{d\beta}{dt}$, where $t^* = \bar{\mu}\epsilon_f \Delta x^2 / (p_s^2 v_a)$, versus the aspect ratio of the chain

Figure 3. The formation time t/t^* of a whole chain versus the distance between the electrodes, where $t^* = \bar{\mu}\epsilon_f \Delta x^2 / (p_s^2 v_a)$